

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 110

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 110

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 110:0 A Psalm of David.</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">Psa. 110:1 לְדָוִד מִזְמוֹר נְאֻם יְהוָה </p>
<p>Psa. 110:1 “The LORD says to my Lord: <i>“^bSit at My right hand Until I make ‘Your enemies a footstool for Your feet.’”</i> ² The LORD will stretch forth Your strong <i>“scepter from Zion, saying,</i> <i>“^bRule in the midst of Your enemies.”</i> ³ Your <i>“people</i> ¹will volunteer freely in the day of Your ²power; <i>^bIn ³holy array, from the womb of the dawn,</i> ⁴Your youth are to You <i>as the ‘dew.</i></p>	<p>לְאֲדֹנָי שֵׁב לְיְמִינֵי עַד-אֲשֵׁית אֲזִכְיָךְ הַיָּמִים לְרִגְלֶיךָ : ² מִטְּהַ-עֵזְבֶךָ יִשְׁלַח יְהוָה מִצִּיּוֹן רֹדֶה בְּקֶרֶב אֲזִכְיָךְ : ³ עֲמֹנָה נְדָבַת בְּיוֹם חַיִּלְךָ בְּתֹדֵרֵי-קֶדֶשׁ מִרְחֹם מִשְׁתַּח לְךָ טַל יִלְדְּתִיךָ : ⁴ נִשְׁבַּע יְהוָה וְלֹא יִנָּחֵם אֶתְהַ-כֹּתֵן לְעוֹלָם עַל-דְּבַרְתִּי מִלְכֵי-צָדֵק : ⁵ אֲדֹנָי עַל-יְמִינֶךָ מִחֵץ בְּיוֹם-אֲפֹ מְלָכִים : ⁶ יַדְוִן בַּגּוֹיִם מְלֵא גִוְיוֹת מִחֵץ רֹאשׁ עַל- אֶרֶץ רַבָּה : ⁷ מִנְחַל בְּיַרְדֵּן יִשְׁתָּה עַל-כֶּן יָרִים רֹאשׁ :</p>
<p>Psa. 110:4 “The LORD has sworn and will <i>not</i> ¹change His mind, <i>“You are a ‘priest forever According to the order of Melchizedek.”</i> ⁵ The Lord is <i>at</i> Your right hand; He ¹will <i>shatter</i> kings in the <i>‘day of His wrath.</i> ⁶ He will <i>judge</i> among the nations, He ¹will fill <i>them</i> with <i>corpses,</i> He ²will <i>shatter</i> the ³chief men over a broad country. ⁷ He will <i>drink</i> from the brook by the wayside; Therefore He will <i>lift up His</i> head.</p>	

References

Psalm 110:1

^aMatt 22:44; Mark 12:36; Luke 20:42, 43; Acts 2:34, 35; Heb 1:13

^bMatt 26:64; Eph 1:20; Col 3:1; Heb 1:3; 8:1; 10:12; 12:2

^c1 Cor 15:25; Eph 1:22

Psalm 110:2

^aPs 45:6; Jer 48:17; Ezek 19:14

^bPs 2:9; 72:8; Dan 7:13, 14

Psalm 110:3

¹Lit *will be freewill offerings*

²Or *army*

³Or *the splendor of holiness*

⁴Or *The dew of Your youth is Yours*

^aJudg 5:2; Neh 11:2

^b1 Chr 16:29; Ps 96:9

^c2 Sam 17:12; Mic 5:7

Psalm 110:4

¹Lit *be sorry*

^aHeb 7:21

^bNum 23:19

^cZech 6:13; Heb 5:6, 10; 6:20; 7:17, 21

Psalm 110:5

¹Or *has shattered*

^aPs 16:8; 109:31

^bPs 68:14; 76:12

^cPs 2:5, 12; Rom 2:5; Rev 6:17

Psalm 110:6

¹Or *has filled*

²Or *has shattered*

³Lit *head over*

^aIs 2:4; Joel 3:12; Mic 4:3

^bIs 66:24

^cPs 68:21

Targum

Psa. 110:1 Composed by David, a psalm. The LORD said in his decree to make me lord of all Israel, but he said to me, “Wait still for Saul of the tribe of Benjamin to die, for one reign must not encroach on [another; and afterwards I will make your enemies a prop for your feet.” ANOTHER TARGUM: The LORD spoke by his decree to give me the dominion in exchange for sitting in study of Torah. “Wait at my right hand until I make your enemies a prop for your feet.” ANOTHER TARGUM: The LORD said in his decree to appoint me ruler over Israel, but the LORD said to me, “Wait for Saul of the tribe of Benjamin to pass away from the world; and afterwards you will inherit the kingship, and I will make your enemies a prop for your feet.”² The LORD will send from Zion the rod of your strength, and you will rule in the midst of your enemies.³ Your people are those of the house of Israel who devote themselves to the Torah; you will be helped in the day of your making battle with them; in the glories of holiness the mercies of God will hasten to you like the descent of dew; your offspring dwell securely.⁴ The LORD has sworn and will not turn aside, that you are appointed leader in the age to come, because of the merit that you were a righteous king.⁵ The presence of the LORD is at your right hand; he struck down kings on the day of his anger.⁶ He was appointed judge over the Gentiles; the earth is full of the bodies of the slain wicked; he smote the heads of kings on the earth, very many.⁷ He will receive instruction from the mouth of the prophet on the way; because of this, he will lift up his head.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

Midrash Shocher Tov has an interesting interpretation of the Psalm. It is presented as a hymn of gratitude from the LORD to Abraham. The LORD calls Abraham “my master.” The Midrash explains that the nations of the world were asleep, preventing them from recognizing the LORD. It was Abraham who woke them up to the LORD’s presence. If this did not happen, the Creation would have amounted to nothing. The LORD created the universe so the people could know of His presence. The knowledge and presence of the LORD through the Sefirot are a gift to humanity. What good is a gift of this nature if it is never recognized?

Verse one

לְדָוִד (l'david) – means “to David.” The NASB translated this verse as “A psalm of David.” Hirsch translates it as “to David, a psalm.” This verse is incorrectly translated in Christian Bibles because the church uses this verse to exemplify Jesus Christ as the Messiah who sits on the right hand of the LORD God. The Psalm was written to David and not by David. Therefore, the correct translation is:

To David. A Psalm. The LORD said to my master: Wait at My right hand, until I make your enemies your footstool.

לְאֲדֹנָי (ladonee) – means “my master.” In this verse, the master is a reference to King David. It was common for a person working in the royal court to address the King in this manner.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

